

Mortality amongst Covid 19 Patients in Relation to their Vaccination Status

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Abstract:- COVID 19 causes health as well as an economic burden all over the world causing significant mortality and morbidity. The second wave of COVID 19 occurred in March 2021 in India causing large numbers of severe infections and also the vaccination drive was started during January 2021. Previous studies proved that various factors were associated with mortality and this study was conducted with the objective of estimating the prevalence of mortality and also the factors associated with it, especially in relation to the vaccination status. **Methodology:** A cross-sectional study was conducted in a tertiary care hospital among the COVID 19 patients during the months of June and July 2021. A semi-structured questionnaire was used containing the basic details about the patient and the relevant clinical details. A universal sampling method was employed and those patients who were below the age of 18 years were excluded. Data collected were entered in MS-Excel and analysis was done using SPSS software version 21. **Results:** A total of 226 patients were included in the study. Most of the study subjects were in the age group of >45% (73.5%) and the majority were males. Nearly 42 % of them had any one of the co-morbidities and only 11.5 % of them were vaccinated against COVID 19. The prevalence of mortality was 21.2% and the factors associated were age, co-morbidity status, duration of hospital stay, disease severity, and the vaccination status. **Conclusion-** Vaccination against COVID 19 had less risk of mortality even though other factors could influence it. Hence further research is needed to explore other factors that might affect both morbidity and mortality.

Keywords:- COVID 19, mortality, vaccination status, second wave, hospital stay *Introduction.*

I. INTRODUCTION

COVID 19 was declared a public health emergency by the World Health Organization because of its rapid spreading crossing the international border from Wuhan city of China to all other countries globally 1, 2. It can cause infections in multiple systems especially respiratory tract in humans, such as severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) and Middle East respiratory syndrome². Also there are various factors contributing to the mysterious nature of the disease such as the peculiar biology of infection, longer incubation time along with early and sustained load of virus, occurrence of mild or asymptomatic carriers, shedding of virus for days after the symptom relief⁴. Because of all the above mentioned factors there occurs a difficulty in early diagnosis and management of the

affected patients which could affect the preventive measures employed. There occurs burden all over the world both in terms of health and wealth due to the ill effects of this disease causing significant mortality and morbidity 2,3,10. Based on the WHO data the mortality rate during the pandemic varies from country to country ranging from 0.1 % to 25%.⁴ As of March 2022, there are 446 million cases and 6 million deaths occurred reported all over the world ⁶.

In India, the second wave of COVID pandemic occurred in March 2021 with large numbers in terms of severity at hospitals. Although there is no definitive treatment for COVID 19, steroids have been used based on the experience with influenza and SARS-COV. Infection control measures as advised by the CDC and the WHO guidelines includes hand hygiene and the use of the sanitizers containing the isopropyl alcohol, using the personal protective equipment such as triple layer mask along with effective health education. Though all these measures are effective in controlling the COVID disease, effective control cannot be made since all these are based on the individuals perceptiveness on whether they are accepting and following or not⁴. But vaccination will be effective in not preventing but at least reducing the disease severity ¹¹. In India, vaccination drives are started from January 2021 with initial priority given to the health care and frontline workers which was later extended towards the elderly population and people aged above 45 years. COVID vaccination was provided for all people 18 years of age and above also as of June 2021 ⁵⁻⁸. Significant immunity was observed in both previously infected and naïve subjects which varies from 92 % in documented infection, 92 % in severe disease, and 87 % in case of hospitalized patients¹³⁻¹⁷. Previous studies showed that numerous factors⁹ were associated with mortality in COVID 19 and we conducted this study to find the association between the vaccination status and mortality amongst the COVID patients.

II. METHODOLOGY

A cross-sectional study was conducted in a medical college and hospital situated in Tamil Nadu, South India. The study populations were all the patients with RT-PCR proven COVID- 19 infection and admitted to the Hospital. Those patients who were in the age group less than 18 years were excluded from the study since the vaccination was not approved for that age group. The study duration was between the months of June and July in the year 2021.

A semi-structured questionnaire containing the basic patient details, co-morbidity status, vaccination status, and

the severity of the disease was used. The severity of the disease was assessed using the guidelines given by the Ministry of health and family welfare for the management of COVID patients 12. Universal sampling method was employed based upon which all those patients' admitted during June and July months of 2021 were taken. Based on the exclusion criteria such as age less than 18 years and those who didn't give the informed consent, a total of 227 patients were included in the study at the end.

Data were collected and entered in the MS-Excel and analyzed using the SPSS software version 21. Descriptive statistics were used to determine the frequencies of the study variables and to construct pie charts and bar charts. Association between the various factors especially vaccination status and mortality was analyzed by Chi-

square test of proportion with the P-value at 0.05 and the confidence interval was set at 95 %.

III. RESULTS

The study included 226 patients admitted during the two months in the tertiary care hospital which contains all the patients with all forms of mild, moderate, and severe COVID infection. Table 1 shows the patient basic details and clinical details in which more than two-thirds of the study subjects were above the age of 45 years. The majority (58.8%) were males and 93 participants (41.2%) had any one of the co-morbidities. With regards to the number of days of hospital stay, more than four-fifth of the study subjects were under hospital admission less than 7 days.

S.No	Characteristics	Dead (N- 48)	Live (N-178	Total N-226	Chi-square value	P value
1	Age <45 yrs >45 yrs	2 (3.3%) 46 (27.7%)	58 (96.7%) 120(72.3%)	60 166	15.65	<0.05*
2	Gender Female Male	22 (23.6%) 26(19.5%)	71 (76.4%) 107(80.5%)	93 133	0.552	0.458
3.	Co-morbidity status Yes No	34(25.5%) 14 (15%)	99 (74.5%) 79 (85%)	133 93	3.614	0.5792
4	Disease severity Moderate& below Severe	0 (0%) 48(87.2%)	171(100%) 7 (12.8%)	171 55	191.3	<0.05**
5.	No of hospital stay <7 days >7 days	29 (15%) 19(57.5%)	164(85%) 14(42.5%)	193 33	30.501	<0.05*
6.	Vaccination status Not Vaccinated Vaccinated	48(64.8%) 0(0%)	26(35.2%) 152(100%)	74 152	7.923	<0.05**

Table 1: Basic characteristics of study subjects (N-226)

S.no	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	Age <20 yrs 20-45 46-60 >60 yrs	12 48 77 89	5.3% 21.2 34% 39.5%
2	Gender Male female	133 93	58.8% 41.2%
3	Co-morbidities Yes No	93 133	41.2% 58.8%
4	No of Hospital stays: <7 days >7 days	193 33	85.4% 14.6%

Table 2 – Association between the study variables and mortality status (N-227)

Fig 1- shows the vaccination status of the subjects in which only 26 participants had been vaccinated which contributes only 11.5% of the total study population. Fig 2- shows the severity of the COVID infection in which the majority (42%) had the moderate form of the disease and only 24.4% had a severe form of the disease and the remaining patients belonged to the milder form of the infection. Hence the severe form of the disease among the study subjects is considerably less which is only 24.4%.

Table 2 shows that the study subjects with the age more than 45 years had higher mortality when compared to those aged less than 45 years. Also those who had severe forms of disease had higher risk of mortality. The study subjects with hospital stay of less than 7 days and those who were vaccinated were at less risk of death when compared to the others. The above findings were found to be statistically significant at P value less than 0.05. There was no gender association and also no association of the presence of the co-morbidity with the mortality status of the study subjects.

Fig. 1: Vaccination status of study subjects (N-227)

*significant at p value <0.05 (Chi square test)
 **Significant at p value <0.05 (Likelihood ratio)

Fig. 2: Severity of COVID infection of the study subjects (N-227)

IV. DISCUSSION

The results of our study showed that the overall mortality of the admitted patients during the study period was 21.2 % which is nearly equal to a similar study conducted in New Delhi by Muthukrishnan J et al 13 which was depicted as 28.4 % of patients died. Also in the present study, those who were belonged to mild and moderate forms of disease never died. This clearly explains that only severe forms of the COVID infection were associated with mortality as shown in table 2. These findings were consistent with the various other studies which explained the similar findings¹⁵⁻¹⁹. Thus it is important to screen the patients and categorize the patients based upon their severity illness such as number of symptoms, nature of symptoms like breathlessness and the involvement of lungs so that prioritization can be given and effective management is possible.

In the present study, we identified there is an increased risk of mortality with increasing age and also the presence of morbidity in the patients affected by COVID-19. These findings were contrary to findings of the study conducted in a similar setting by Rastad et al 14 which showed that the presence of diabetes had more risk of developing death. These differences could be due the fact that in our study, we considered only the presence of co-morbidity as a factor that was significant. Also these difference in the findings could be the due to the different study setting Hence the patients with old age and those with known co-morbidity should be given higher priority for the management since they are at higher risk of developing mortality though there are various factors that could contribute to the death of the patients.

Previous studies conducted during trials and the real world data depicted that there is less possibility of having the severe forms of the disease and thus low mortality among those who are vaccinated against the COVID-19²⁰⁻²². Our study showed less mortality rate among those who were under hospital stay of less than 7 days. The vaccine effectiveness of the Astra Zeneca (ChAdOx1 nCoV-19) vaccine has shown to be as 80% in terms of the Hospitalization²³. COVISHIELD vaccine has been proved to be effective in preventing the infection by 80-94%²⁴. The current study finding of risk of hospitalization is also supported by a study done by Carrillo-Vega MF et al²⁵. These findings indirectly tells that with decrease in the number of days of hospitalization which could be due to the less severity and added factors such as vaccination there is increase in the successful rate of treatment thus decreasing the rate of COVID mortality.

In the present study, the vaccinated individuals though a very small proportion might fall into the severe forms of the disease but they never end their life. This clearly explains the importance of vaccination helps in reducing the severity of the disease which indirectly helps in reducing the mortality. There are many limitations in the current study. One of them is that we didn't take into account the number of doses of vaccination and the type of vaccines since the effectiveness differs based upon these

facts. Also, the study was done during the initial days immediately after the vaccination drive comes into action and hence many of the population would not be vaccinated. And since it was performed in a hospital the findings cannot be externally validated to the general population. But the findings of this study could help the researchers to take into the various factors that could contribute the mortality of the patients affected by COVID.

V. CONCLUSION

Thus the findings of the study showed that there is no mortality among the vaccinated patients affected by COVID which implies that vaccination is as effective in reducing mortality. This study also depicted that the factors such as increasing age, presence of co-morbidity, severity duration of hospital stay should be considered while predicting mortality among the COVID-19 infected patients. Thus the effective vaccination against COVID infection should be promoted among the general public. Effective health education could help in acceptance of COVID vaccine since there is still stigma around the world especially among the developing countries like India. The study findings could help the researchers to highlight the importance of the COVID vaccination so that behavior towards the accepting vaccination can be changed among the public and this long prevailing global COVID pandemic could be brought under control

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